

Intercultural dialogue in school mathematics: Ethics of school-free data collection

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Our project aims to promote intercultural dialogue in school mathematics, by exploring the experiences of migrant students and teachers in mathematics classrooms. Although data collection was initially designed to be conducted in person, some ethical issues have emerged as it moved online, due to the COVID-19 pandemic. This poster explores a series of 4 ethical considerations: a) the “shielding” role of school making some injustices invisible, b) the mediating role of school around the relationships that researchers need to create with the families, c) the consideration of the value of different mathematical knowledges, and d) some, practical issues.

We endeavour to study the impact of student migration on mathematics learning from the perspectives of students and teachers. There is an existing and growing body of research focusing on challenges in relation to migration in mathematics classrooms (Barwell, 2016). We aim to examine the potential richness afforded by students’ multiple cultural, linguistic and educational experiences of mathematics, including different ways of doing, learning and thinking mathematics. This poster description is organised as follows: we first describe the project and its goals, we then elaborate on the data collection methods and how they changed due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and we finally discuss four ethical issues which emerged in relation to this transition.

A few words about the project: Migration in mathematics classrooms

More than 500,000 children in Canada come from migrant backgrounds (Statistics Canada, 2011) and all must study mathematics. For this study, we define migrant students as those who, as a result of a change of residence, experience differences of culture and language in

Please cite as: Abtahi, Y., Barwell, R., Suurtamm, C., Kane, R., Assaf, F., Pitsili-Chatzi, D., & Mbodje, A. (2021). Intercultural dialogue in school mathematics: Ethics of school-free data collection. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 247–251). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5457168>

school. Thus, migrant students include those whose families have moved for economic or employment reasons, those whose families are escaping war or other disasters as refugees and asylum-seekers, and indigenous students whose families have moved between a rural indigenous setting and an urban school. How does migration affect students' and teachers' experiences of school mathematics? Research suggests that many students from immigrant backgrounds face challenges in mathematics and underachieve. We conjecture that the mathematics teachers of migrant students often have little understanding of what their students are experiencing or what mathematics they already know. Migrant students can find the culture of teaching and learning mathematics quite alien, may bring novel ways of doing mathematics, and may encounter new ways of thinking about mathematics. Cultural differences in mathematics classrooms lead teachers to feel uncertain and unprepared. In an extension to the research on migration in mathematics classrooms, we aim to a. understand the experiences of students and teachers of learning and teaching mathematics in the context of migration b. promote dialogue between students and teachers in relation to these experiences and observe the impact of this dialogue on teachers' practice. The study inspires to stimulate multivocal, intercultural dialogue between students and teachers of mathematics, and helps us understand the impact of migration on the learning and teaching of mathematics. In the context of increasing mobility and superdiverse mathematics classrooms (Barwell, 2016), the study aims to create conversational relationship among families, children, teachers and school systems, in relation to learning and teaching of mathematics, as well as to highlight "unfamiliar" maths for teachers and for students.

Data collection: Pre-COVID and post-COVID

Originally, participants were being recruited from ten different schools and data collection to be in schools. After schools closed as a precautionary measure for COVID-19, this was no longer possible. Instead, we are recruiting participants through organisations which serve migrant populations and data collection is conducted online.

The initial pre-COVID design of the data collection

In the initial design of this study, there were two phases of data collection: the first phase would involve students and the second phase would involve teachers. In the first phase, our group would visit 10 schools and work with 5 students in each school. These students, would take the role of co-researchers, gathering accounts of their own prior and current experiences of mathematics, from their parents, and in their mathematics classes. Towards the end of our meetings, students would synthesize their collective experiences in the form of collages, in order to communicate their experiences with teachers. At the end of the group meetings, each student would be interviewed to gain their individual perspective. The second phase would focus on teachers' experiences. We would share each collage with teachers from the school, to understand teachers' responses to students' experiences of migration. Teachers, as co-researchers, would collect observations of their own practice, noting shifts arising from their new understanding of their migrant students' experiences. At the end of this phase,

teachers from the 10 participating classes would compare the collages created in their schools, their responses to them, and the resulting shifts in their practice in focus groups.

The post-COVID emerging data collection practice

As the study moved online due to the pandemic, the two data collection phases (one for students and one for teachers) are maintained but their character has changed. In the first phase, we hold ten virtual math clubs with six children in each club. Each group will meet virtually for five sessions and engage in both synchronous tasks as well as “take home” activities to work on with parents/siblings and to share at the next session. At the end of each math club, we hold interviews with each student and – if they want – a family member. The second phase, teachers’ experiences, will include six virtual groups of mathematics teachers who will meet twice. We will share and discuss the student participant profiles with teachers as well as examples illustrating children’s cultural-historical repertoires with respect to mathematics. Teachers will be asked to reflect on information shared, their reactions, and implications for practice.

Ethical considerations emerging

The transition to online data collection made visible to us a series of ethical considerations. As we are currently in the first phase of data collection, working with students, these ethical considerations are related to data collection with students.

The location of data collection changes from school to home

As the location of data collection changes from school to the virtual space (as students and researchers are physically at their home), aspects of the role of school are made visible to us. School conceals differences among students; the four walls of the school appear to be shielding students from these differences and to offer a sense of security. Inspired by Fasheh’s (1998) question “Which is more fundamental? Outward peace or being true to our humanity?”, we ask: What sort of an “outward peace” is created by schools and what becomes invisible by this portrayal of peace? What deeply rooted inequalities are given permission to be ignored in an “equal school”? For example, to identify potential participants, we visited richer and poorer parts of the city. This process made visible differences in the living spaces among students, which are concealed in school. We do not intend to evaluate this school function as “good” or “bad”; instead, we try to think about its complex social implications.

Relationships with children and their families are no longer mediated by school.

To conduct any research projects, relationships need to be built between researchers and participants, while in projects related to the concerns of the MES community, we hope that these relationships extend beyond whatever is necessary to obtain data from students or communities. The transition of data collection location made visible to us the school’s role in facilitating the building of these relations. If we had been able to continue with research in schools – and given that at least one of the schools were participating based on established

relationships – the schools would mediate the relationship between researchers and students and their families. Due to the pandemic, we are attempting an online approach that reaches out to families directly using the connections we have in the group. When school stops mediating the relationship between researchers and children/families, questions arise: What is the nature of school’s mediating role in building relationships between researchers and families? If the school is not there, for example at the time of COVID-19, how can/should researchers manage relationships with families and children?

Different mathematical knowledges are valued differently

Whose mathematical knowledge is highlighted? Our data collection methods entail doing mathematical activities with students with a migration background. While designing, conducting, and reflecting on these mathematical exchanges, a tension emerges about whose mathematics is highlighted. We acknowledge that these tensions cannot be resolved. We all bring our ideas and experiences of mathematics – our repertoires – to the project, and we ‘see’ participants’ repertoires through our own. But we ask: whose knowledge counts as mathematical knowledge? (Abtahi, 2019). Extending the above line of thought, we are also thinking about what mathematical knowledge is valued. Walkerdine’s “commodity” perspective draws our attention to how knowing the mathematics of the curriculum not only worths much more than other kinds of mathematics, but knowing “other kinds of mathematics” is often considered to be deficient and of lower level (Walkerdine, 1990).

Practicalities of online data collection

Finally, ethical concerns also emerge in relation to the practicalities of data collection. As many students’ activities have moved online and students spend a lot of time in front of the screen, a question emerges about the ethical implications of asking students to spend more time online. Furthermore, issues emerge related to who has access to and who has comfort with technology, as well as the implications of video-recording students while they are physically at their homes.

Concluding thoughts

Through this poster, we present some ethical issues and dilemmas that have emerged in relation to our study’s data collection transitioning from in-person to online. We hope that the conversations with the MES community will not only help us reflect on the ethical dilemmas that we are facing, but will also open up the discussion about ethical issues related to data collection in the cyber space and beyond.

Acknowledgement

This research is funded by Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council (SSHRC) in Canada.

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